

ISic1468

I.Sicily inscription 1468

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

tufa limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἀγασία ἔμ

2. ἰ τὸ σᾶμα τ

3. ὁ Καρία οἴ

4. μοι

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284885

EDR 108696

EDCS 41300068

EDCS 64700407

PHI 175680

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